

A NOTE ON *m*-BROMOPHENYLTHIOUREA AND ITS MERCURATED DERIVATIVES

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Although the synthesis and the properties of *o*- and *p*-bromophenylthioureas have been described in the literature (Dyson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 436; 1924, 128, 1702; Shimotani, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 72, 328), the preparation of *m*-bromo analogue does not appear to have been previously recorded. The *m*-bromophenylthiourea has now been synthesised by heating *m*-bromoaniline hydrochloride with ammonium sulphocyanide in aqueous medium.

In view of the possible fungicidal action of thiourea (Horsfall, "Fungicides and their action"; *Chronica Botanica Co.* 1945, p. 126) and *N*-substituted monoarylthioureas (Shimotani, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 72, 919) and the commercial use of mercurated thiourea as fungicide under the trade name of 'Lunasan' (McCallan *et al.*, *Phytopath.*, 1955, 45, 299), the synthesis of mercurated derivatives of the above thiourea has been undertaken with the expectation that they may show promising fungicidal activity.

The *m*-bromophenylthiourea has been mercurated using mercuric acetate to afford an acetoxymercuri compound. On the basis of earlier observations on the mercuration of aromatic amines (Newton Friend; "Text-book of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. XI, 1928, Part I) and arylthioureas (Guha Sircar and Patnaik, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 535), it has been assumed that the acetoxymercuri group enters the aryl nucleus at the *para* position (with respect to -NH group).

This acetoxymercuri compound has been converted into chloro- and bromo-mercuri compounds since a few of the chloromercuri compounds had been found earlier to be more effective than the corresponding acetoxymercuri derivatives.

The chloromercuri compound has been prepared by Bruce's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 593), by adding sodium chloride to the reaction mixture from which the acetoxymercuri compound is to be isolated.

The bromomercuri compound has been prepared in a similar way, by adding a concentrated solution of KBr to the reaction mixture from which the acetoxymercuri compound is to be isolated.

***m*-Bromophenylthiourea.**—*m*-Bromoaniline (3.6 g.) and HCl (conc., 8 c.c.) were taken in a conical flask and water (60-80 c.c.) was added to dissolve the hydrochloride on heating. NH₄SCN (7 g.) was added to the hydrochloride solution and the whole mixture was refluxed on a boiling water-bath for 2 to 3 hours, when a white precipitate appeared. It was collected by filtration and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in white, glistening, light-weight plates, m.p. 138°, yield 80%. It is soluble in alcohol and bitter in taste. (Found: Br, 34.81; S, 13.53. Calc. Br, 34.65; S, 13.85 per cent).

p-Acetoxymercuri-*m*-bromophenylthiourea.—*m*-Bromophenylthiourea (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol-dilute acetic acid solution and was treated with an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (2.8 g. in 40 c.c. water), acidified with acetic acid. There was immediate precipitation. The reaction mixture was kept overnight. The precipitate was collected and washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with alcohol and very dilute acetic acid, m.p. 275-76°, yield 75%. (Found: Hg, 40.73. Calc. Hg, 40.89 per cent).

p-Chloromercuri-*m*-bromophenylthiourea.—Acetic acid (4.8 g.) was treated with NaHCO₃ (2.5 g.) and diluted with 30 c.c. of water (p_H 4.3) and to that mercuric acetate (3.2 g.) was added, followed by *m*-bromophenylthiourea (1 g.), dissolved in alcohol and dilute acetic acid. On addition of a concentrated solution of sodium chloride (2.5 g. in 10 c.c. water) to the above mixture, a white precipitate appeared. The reaction mixture was set aside for 24 hours. It was then filtered and washed thoroughly with hot water, followed by alcohol, m.p. > 350°, yield 70%. (Found: Hg, 42.98. Calc. Hg, 42.96 per cent).

p-Bromomercuri-*m*-bromophenylthiourea.—The method was exactly the same as above excepting that KBr solution was employed in place of NaCl; m.p. > 350°, yield 65%. (Found: Hg, 39.69. Calc. Hg, 39.21 per cent).

Bactericidal Test.—The Rideal-Walker serial drop dilution method was used for assaying the antibacterial action of the acetoxy-, chloro- and bromo-mercuri compounds. The test organisms were 24 hours' culture of *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The acetoxy- and chloro- and bromo-mercuri compounds were found to be active in dilutions 1:80,000, 1:100,000 and 1:100,000 respectively.

Fungicidal Test.—For assaying the fungicidal activity, the method of Montgomery and Moore (*J. Pomol. Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 15, 253) with a slight modification was used. *Piricularia orizae*, Cav., the causative organism of the blast of rice, was used as the test fungus. The mercurated compounds were found to possess good fungicidal activity, the percentage inhibition of spore germination being cent per cent at 100 p.p.m in case of *m*-(bromophenylthiourea) and 4-5 p.p.m with the acetoxy-, chloro- and bromo-mercuri compounds.

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